

DECENT WORKING CONDITIONS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: “THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB SATISFACTION AND MENTAL HEALTH”

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Abstract: This academic paper contains the information related to the relationship between job satisfaction and mental health. Moreover, it gives you opportunity to get familiarized with causes and effects of poor working conditions not only for certain individuals but also for the whole country.

Key words: working conditions, poor, decent, working staff, individual, health, mental health, country's economy.

Аннотация: Данная научная статья содержит информацию о связи между удовлетворенностью от работы и ментальным здоровьем. Более того, вы можете быть ознакомлены с причинами и следствии негодных рабочих условий труда не только для определенной личности, но и целой страны.

Ключевые слова: рабочие условия, негодный, достойный, личность, здоровье, ментальное здоровье, экономика страны.

Being born to this world each of us has certain rights and obligations. We have full right for living, for being free in our opinions and views (in frames of law), for being taught, treated. In one line with life, health, education, there also should be put - satisfaction from workplace. People have several main aspects of life such as health, family, friends, finances and job. In its turn, the last two are connected to each other more closely than we are able to imagine. The bond between job satisfaction and life satisfaction is strong enough to be discussed.

The job satisfaction is the level of indicating how much the person is satisfied from the place he/she is currently working at. The job satisfaction depends on

working conditions. The working conditions include certain criteria such as safety of job, administration's attitude, friendly staff and, indeed, wage rate [4]. When a worker is surrounded with good working conditions, he/she is able to increase the level of productivity and this in its turn, is predicted to up the profit of a certain company. Job safety is the priority number one among others because a worker should feel himself/herself safe in order to create. The administration of the company plays a great role in flourishing the company. Boss's recognition and attitude to the working staff influences the level of the job satisfaction positively. The salary rate is also a one of main key factors in job satisfaction. The higher the wage is, the more satisfied the worker[2].

Unfortunately, not always and not everywhere we are able to victim that all abovementioned criterions are fully provided to the working staff. Sometimes people work for companies where the administration's attitude is egoistic and haughtily, shortage of working equipment, every day is risking and not safe, in addition to all those, the salary is at a minimum rate. Even if everything is poor in the company/factory, it is required to be more tolerating by working staff and forget about their labor rights [2]. In developing countries there can be observed workplace deficit. Subsequently, people are forced by outer circumstances to accept not suitable conditions in order that their families can have some bread on a table.

Working and being in such workplace, people are likely to acquire different kinds of diseases. Obviously, diseases may be connected to the physical health in parallel to mental one. If heart attack, low blood circulation, overweight are considered to be physical illnesses, burnout, and depression, bipolar disorder are one of mental illnesses caused by poor workplace conditions [1]. When a person has some physical health problems, it is recommended to visit a physician. In time taken pills and injection are highly efficient to cure physical diseases. Furthermore, if we have any mental disorder, it is not easily seen to others [1]. Individuals may live their regular life, but one day there can be news about his/her suicide or at minimum to be at psychiatric disorders hospital. Unfortunately, not only an individual is predicted to suffer from poor working circumstances, but also people around do. According to

world statistics, about 14% of all families around the world face divorce because of mental illness of one who works in unpleasant place [5]. The majority of people bring their work problems to home. Such people are angry to the people around: their family (parents, children, siblings and spouses), friends, neighbors and even sometimes strangers realize how much effort they put in their work, they do not get worthy feedback [1]. In addition, the worst thing is that people working in such atmosphere understand that they do not have another better option. They are induced themselves to continue working in order to earn money.

However, being surrounded with poor working conditions, working staff is not concerned about bettering economic growth of the company they are currently are working for. Consequently, there occurs such chain: poor working conditions-poor worker-poor company-poor country [3]. As a result, not only one individual suffers but also families, communities, societies and even whole countries are highly likely to perceive economic degradation. When everyone in a company cares about only his/her financial benefit, this situation creates opportunities to lower the quality of manufactured products. This, in its, turn, leads to decreasing the rate of demand by foreign countries and as a result the export as well as trade turnover may be lowered. Export and outer trade turnover decide the lion portion of economic state of the country. So, we by the help of analysis can create such chain as: the higher foreign demand is, the higher export is; the higher export is, the higher external trade is; the higher external trade is, the higher foreign trade turnover is; the higher foreign trade turnover is, the richer a country is. The worst issue there that this chain is an endless cycle where one cell depends on a previous one.

As we can see, the poor working conditions are able to lead to disastrous results touching the majority of social fields starting from mental health ending with regression of country economy [3]. Therefore, there are should be created decent working conditions anywhere the person is working at. They are followings: safety of doing job, career promotion, administration’s right attitude, decent wage rate, providing with all the necessary equipments and I would like to add one more, friendly atmosphere in the working staff.

If the job is safe, people wouldn't worry about danger, vice versa, they would be more engaged in working processes. For example, teachers won't be able to teach target audiences while there is a war outside.

If there is a career promotion, an individual will try to achieve further aims related to the career. Where there is a healthy competition among colleagues, there is a growth and development. However, at some companies there is monarchy system and others don't have any chances to be promoted. And it is illogical to do their best as they waste their time and efforts in vain.

If there is a fair administration that values the efforts a working staff is making and have fair attitude towards his/her subordinate staff, the people working for a certain company respect and obey the boss.

If there is a decent salary that is a proper to the inflation of money, a worker should not worry about future and tries to get more involved in the working process. Furthermore, according to the questionnaires held among big companies' workers in 2019, the salary is seen as a great motivation to work more efficiently.

If there is no shortage of working equipment, people less feel stressed. As we are living and working in a digital era, all the necessary devices should be provided by a company. Due not to having enough equipment at workplace such as laptops, printers, personal computers and etc., a worker feel anxiety since he/she ought to purchase all them by himself or herself.

If there is a friendly atmosphere in a working staff, a person gets support and motivation from colleagues. Through colleagues support and polite attitude, a worker feels himself/herself as an important part of whole team and can share his/her problems to get them solved. Teambuilding trainings and corporative events are helpful to gain the workers and give the sense of a big friendly and supportive family.

In conclusion, decent working conditions are able to create a successful results and people are able to build a flourishing country. However, poor working conditions are likely to destroy a person's life and respectively cause damage to the economy of a country.

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